

In vitro embryo production alters spatial organization of mesodermal and endodermal markers in elongating bovine conceptuses

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In brief

Embryo production technologies can affect early developmental processes critical for pregnancy establishment in cattle. This study reveals that in vitro-derived embryos exhibit impaired elongation and altered lineage patterning compared to those derived from artificial insemination.

Abstract

This study aimed to characterize and compare cell lineage specification in the embryonic disc (ED) of elongating bovine conceptuses derived from artificial insemination or from in vitro-produced embryos, including fresh and cryopreserved blastocysts. Conceptuses were recovered on day 16 of gestation, measured, and EDs were dissected for whole-mount immunofluorescence using markers of epiblast, mesoderm, and endoderm lineages. Image analysis was performed to assess disc morphometry, epiblast cell number, and spatial organization of lineage-specific markers. Conceptuses derived from artificial insemination were longer and exhibited larger EDs compared to those derived following transfer of in vitro-produced embryos, particularly vitrified embryos, which showed reduced elongation and altered disc morphology. Epiblast cell numbers were lower in vitrified conceptuses but scaled proportionally with disc size across all groups. The initiation of gastrulation and hypoblast differentiation had occurred in most conceptuses, regardless of origin; however, in vitro-produced conceptuses displayed altered spatial organization of mesodermal and endodermal markers, with less defined patterning compared to artificial insemination-derived conceptuses. These findings indicate that while key developmental processes are preserved, in vitro embryo production, especially when combined with cryopreservation, is associated with impaired elongation and disrupted spatial organization of cell lineages during early development. Such alterations may contribute to reduced developmental competence and increased embryonic loss.

Keywords bovine, conceptus elongation, cryopreservation, gastrulation, endoderm differentiation

Introduction

Reproductive efficiency is the main driver of profitability in live-stock production systems (Shalloo et al., 2014). Pregnancy loss, rather than fertilization failure, is one of the major causes of reproductive failure in cattle. Most pregnancy loss in dairy cows occurs during the early stages of development, with 20%–50% occurring in the first week of pregnancy and a further 30% in the second and third weeks (Wiltbank et al., 2016, Berg et al., 2022). These losses are associated with impairments in key developmental and physiological events, including embryonic genome activation and blastocyst formation during the first week, and compromised conceptus elongation, inadequate maternal recognition

of pregnancy, and failure to maintain the corpus luteum during the second and third weeks (Diskin & Morris, 2008, Wiltbank et al., 2016).

The incidence of embryonic loss increases with the use of assisted reproductive technologies such as in vitro embryo production (IVP), where early-stage losses may reach up to 40%–60% in the first month of pregnancy in cattle (Ealy et al., 2019). In a recent field trial comparing pregnancy outcomes after timed artificial insemination or embryo transfer (ET) with IVP embryos, the largest proportion of embryonic loss occurred before day 18 of gestation. In addition, pregnancy loss between days 32 and 62 was greater following transfer of an IVP embryo compared to pregnancies established by artificial insemination, particularly

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when frozen embryos were used; losses after day 62 were minimal ($\leq 3.5\%$) (Crowe et al., 2024, Crowe et al., 2025a). Anomalies during the period of conceptus elongation are strongly implicated in subsequent embryo loss as developmental programmes establish the different embryonic and extra-embryonic lineages that continue to differentiate over time (Mamo et al., 2011, Pfeffer & Pearton, 2012, van Leeuwen et al., 2015, Scatolin et al., 2024). Moreover, this increased loss may be attributable, at least in part, to delayed conceptus attachment (Crowe et al., 2025b).

The early stages of embryonic development in ruminants represent a dynamic and precisely regulated process governed by intricate signalling mechanisms that are critical for the initiation and maintenance of pregnancy. Following fertilization, the embryo undergoes a series of mitotic divisions resulting in the formation of a blastocyst by ~day 7. This stage of development is characterized by cellular differentiation into two different lineages (Pfeffer, 2024); as cells start to reorganize, those located on the outside of the embryo undergo polarization, forming outer polar cells which become the trophoblast (TE), that will form the placenta, and inner apolar cells which become the inner cell mass (ICM), that will give rise to the fetus. This event, known as the first lineage determination, is essential for subsequent development and is conserved among mammals (Hue et al., 2012, Pfeffer, 2018), with the exception of marsupials and monotremes that form a unilaminar blastocyst lacking a defined ICM (Frankenberg et al., 2016). In mice, the Hippo/YAP signalling pathway is then triggered in the outer cells, activating TEA Domain Transcription Factor 4 (TEAD4), which down-regulates SRY-box transcription factor 2 (SOX2) and up-regulates Caudal-type homeobox 2 (CDX2), essential for TE commitment and maturation (Korotkevich et al., 2017, Pérez-Gómez et al., 2021). SOX2 has been described as a conserved pluripotency marker known to be expressed in primordial germ cells and postnatal oocytes in various mammalian species (Campolo et al., 2013). However, its role in ICM formation in bovine embryos is not yet confirmed (Goissis & Cibelli, 2014). At the blastocyst stage, SOX2 expression is restricted to the ICM, as are Octamer-binding transcription factor 4 (OCT4) or Homeobox protein NANOG, which later become epiblast-specific. A second lineage determination event occurs when the ICM commits to the epiblast and the primitive endoderm or hypoblast. SRY-box transcription factor 17 (SOX17) was identified as a reliable marker for early hypoblast formation in cattle; it is co-expressed with GATA binding protein 6 (GATA6) and NANOG in the ICM at the blastocyst stage. At later stages, SOX17 and GATA6 become hypoblast-specific (Canizo et al., 2019).

Post-hatching preimplantation embryo development in ruminants involves transition of the spherical blastocyst to an ovoid, tubular, and finally a filamentous structure due to rapid proliferation of the TE. During conceptus elongation, the epiblast forms the embryo proper, undergoing gastrulation and giving rise to a multi-layered structure, called a gastrula, which includes the three germ layers (mesoderm, ectoderm, and endoderm), whereas the primitive endoderm will form the yolk sac, ensuring nutrient transport (Pérez-Gómez et al., 2021, Pfeffer, 2024). Gastrulation in mammals typically results in a flat embryonic disc (ED) in species such as humans, rabbits, and ungulates, whereas in mice it forms an egg-cylinder structure (Ton et al., 2023). In ruminants, the ED emerges after the epiblast is exposed following the disappearance of Rauber's layer, a polar trophoblast that initially overlays the epiblast (van Leeuwen et al., 2020, Pfeffer, 2022). The ED first appears

as a slightly delineated, translucent structure and later forms a distinct bulge (Maddox-Hyttel et al., 2003). The process of gastrulation begins with epiblast cell ingression to form the primitive streak (PS), followed by involution through the streak to generate mesodermal and endodermal lineages, and is driven by the expression of the T-box-containing transcription factor brachyury (T), reported in vertebrates as an early marker for mesoderm formation, with a transient and migratory pattern that begins at the posterior pole of the ED, later migrating to the derived mesoderm and notochord at the four-somite stage (Hue et al., 2001, van Leeuwen et al., 2015).

Although blastocyst-stage embryos can be easily generated in the laboratory by in vitro fertilization, subsequent post-hatching development, particularly conceptus elongation, is maternally driven. Despite some advances (Ramos-Ibeas et al., 2020, Isaac & Pfeffer, 2021, Isaac et al., 2024), elongation has not been successfully recapitulated in vitro and does not occur in vivo in the absence of functional uterine glands (Gray et al., 2002). Given the critical role of elongation in establishing pregnancy, and its strong association with early embryonic loss, a detailed understanding of normal cell lineage specification, as the embryo transitions from the spherical to the elongated stage and undergoes gastrulation, is essential. However, the extent to which the origin of the embryo influences these early developmental processes and resulting phenotypic outcomes remains unclear. It is likely that errors in conceptus development, gastrulation, and attachment associated with IVP, are associated with the higher incidence of pregnancy loss compared to in vivo-derived embryos. Given the highly dynamic and complex signalling nature of embryonic lineage expression and distribution, the aim of this study was to characterize and compare cell lineage specification in the ED of elongating bovine conceptuses derived from in vivo- versus in vitro-produced embryos.

Materials and methods

Ethics statement

All experimental procedures involving animals were approved by the Animal Research Ethics Committee in University College Dublin and licensed by the Health Products Regulatory Authority, in accordance with Statutory Instrument No. 543 of 2012 under Directive 2010/63/EU on the Protection of Animals used for Scientific Purposes.

Experimental design

The experimental design is illustrated in Figure 1. In vivo-derived (IVD) bovine conceptuses were generated by artificial insemination ($n=28$ heifers) and IVP blastocysts were transferred to synchronized recipient heifers (ET, $n=29$ heifers) on day 7. Recipients were slaughtered in a commercial abattoir on day 16 of pregnancy and elongated conceptuses were recovered by uterine flushing. Day 16 was chosen as it coincides with gastrulation and the establishment of the germ lineages as well as with maternal recognition of pregnancy (Betteridge et al., 1980). Conceptus length was recorded and EDs were located, carefully dissected, and processed for whole-mount immunocytochemical characterization of embryonic lineage specification around the onset of gastrulation. EDs were labelled with

Figure 1 Experimental design. Estrous cycles of heifers were synchronized and heifers received (A) artificial insemination (AI) for the generation of in vivo-derived (IVD) bovine conceptuses ($n=28$ heifers) or (B) in vitro-produced (IVP) blastocysts for the generation of IVP conceptuses ($n=29$ heifers), either FRESH or cryopreserved by slow freezing for direct transfer (DT) or vitrification (VIT). (C) Elongated conceptuses were recovered on day 16 and embryonic discs (EDs) were dissected to characterize embryonic lineage specification by immunofluorescence. The ED appears as a slightly delineated, translucent structure forming a distinct bulge. P4 = progesterone releasing intravaginal device; GnRH = gonadotrophin releasing hormone; PG = prostaglandin F2 α ; ET = embryo transfer; IVM = in vitro maturation; IVF = in vitro fertilization; IVC = in vitro culture; day 0 was considered the day of insemination/fertilization (12–18 hr after the onset of oestrus). Partially created with BioRender.com.

different combinations of a panel of primary antibodies, targeting well-established markers of epiblast (SOX2), PS/mesodermal lineages (T), and hypoblast/endodermal lineages (SOX17 and Forkhead Box protein A2 (FOXA2)).

Embryo production

Oestrous cycles of crossbreed beef heifers were synchronized by a modified Ovsynch protocol using an 8-day progesterone-releasing intravaginal device (PRID[®]E, 1.55 g of progesterone; Ceva Santé Animale, Libourne, France). On the day of insertion of the PRID, heifers received a 2 ml intramuscular injection of a gonadotropin releasing hormone analogue (Ovarelin[®], Ceva Santé Animale). After 6 days, heifers received a 5 ml intramuscular injection of prostaglandin F2 alpha (PGF2 α ; Enzaprost[®]; Ceva Santé Animale) and 24 hr later the PRID was removed, and a second injection of PGF2 α was administered. Heifers were observed for signs of oestrus every 4 hr starting 30 hr after PRID removal and those that showed oestrus were randomly assigned to treatment (artificial insemination or ET). To produce IVD embryos, the artificial insemination group was inseminated (day 0) with frozen-thawed semen from a bull of proven fertility 12–18 hr after the onset of oestrus, and again 6 hr later. Heifers assigned to ET were used as recipients 7 days later.

In vitro embryo production was performed using Stroebech[®] Media products (Hundested, Denmark). Cumulus-oocyte-complexes (COCs) were obtained by follicle aspiration from abattoir-derived ovaries with an 18-gauge needle and a 5 ml sterile syringe. The follicular fluid was placed in 50 ml tubes and, after sedimentation, the COCs were located, washed, and matured in in vitro maturation medium for 24 hr prior to fertilization at 38.8 °C in 5% CO₂ in air. Matured COCs were then fertilized in IVF medium (day 0) with frozen-thawed semen from the same bull used for the generation of IVD embryos, at a concentration of 1×10^6 spermatozoa/ml of IVF medium. After 18–20 hr of incubation in the same conditions described above, presumptive zygotes were denuded and cultured in 50 μ l droplets of IVC medium, covered in heavy oil, at 38.8 °C in an atmosphere of 5% CO₂, 5% O₂, 90% N₂ until day 7 of development. Only grade 1 blastocysts were selected for cryopreservation and/or transfer to synchronized heifers.

Slow freezing and vitrification of blastocysts

Grade 1 blastocysts and expanded blastocysts, following the guidelines of the International Embryo Technology Society, were removed from culture and washed in embryo holding medium

(IMV technologies, L'Aigle, France). Blastocysts were then randomly allocated to one of three groups: no cryopreservation (FRESH, $n=80$), slow freezing for direct transfer (DT, $n=90$), or vitrification (VIT, $n=80$).

Slow freezing was performed using a 1.5 M ethylene glycol solution (BoviFreeze® Minitube, Tiefenbach, Germany) to load the embryos into straws. After equilibration at room temperature (RT) for 10 min, the straws were immersed in isopropyl alcohol at -6°C in an automatic embryo freezing machine (EFT-3002® Portable Embryo Freezer; Beltron Instruments, Longmont, CO, USA). After 2 min at -6°C , ice formation was induced by seeding, after which the straws were maintained for a further 10 min at the same temperature. Following this second equilibration, the temperature was reduced by $-0.5^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to -35°C . Straws were then plunged into liquid nitrogen (LN_2) and maintained at -196°C until thawing. For thawing, straws were removed from LN_2 and held in air for 10 s followed by 30 s immersion in water at 35°C .

Vitrification and warming of embryos was performed following the manufacturer's guidelines (Stroebech® Bovine Embryo Vitrification Kit and Warming Kit). Embryos were washed in sequential droplets of increasing osmolarity and cryoprotectant concentration at a controlled temperature between 25 to 30°C before being placed on the tip of a Cryotop® device (Kitazato, Shizuoka, Japan) and immediately plunged into LN_2 , where they were maintained at -196°C until warming. Warming consisted of submerging the Cryotop® device tip in medium and then transferring the embryos through successive drops of decreasing osmolarity and cryoprotectant concentration.

Generation of day 16 conceptuses

In vitro-derived blastocysts (FRESH, DT, VIT) were transferred to synchronized recipient heifers in groups of 6–10 to the uterine horn ipsilateral to the corpus luteum on day 7 of development. Conceptuses derived from artificial insemination and IVP blastocysts were recovered from the recipients on day 16 following slaughter in a commercial abattoir and flushing of the uterus using pre-warmed phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) (38°C) supplemented with 5% fetal calf serum. Conceptuses were disentangled and measured to record length, and EDs were located and carefully dissected with the use of a scalpel and microsurgical scissors.

Whole-mount immunostaining and confocal imaging

All reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany) unless otherwise stated.

Immediately following dissection, EDs were washed in PBS and fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde (15812-7) for 15 min at RT, washed three times in PBS for 5 min, and permeabilized and blocked in 10% donkey serum, 5% bovine serum albumin (A4378) and 1% Triton X-100 in PBS for 2 hr at RT. Then, they were incubated overnight at 4°C with primary antibodies (Table 1). After four washes of 15 min in 0.2% Triton X-100 in PBS, samples were incubated in the appropriate Alexa Fluor-conjugated secondary antibodies (Table 1) for 2 hr at RT, followed by four 15 min washes in 0.2% Triton X-100 in PBS and counterstained with 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (D9542) for 30 min at RT. Isotype-matched IgG negative controls were included for each biomarker. Finally, samples were mounted on BRAND® cavity slides (BR475505), to preserve embryo shape, in Mowiol® (81381) mounting medium and imaged on a Zeiss LSM 800 Airyscan (Oberkochen, Germany). Images were acquired at 20× magnification, covering the regions of interest with ~ 10 – 15 slices per sample, and z-sections were taken every $5\ \mu\text{m}$.

Image analysis

Images were processed and analysed using Fiji software (Schindelin et al., 2012). 3D cell segmentation was performed independently for each fluorescence channel using a pixel classification software, Ilastik 1.4.1. (Berg et al., 2019), that allows for supervised annotation and batch processing, generating binary mask stacks. Disc length was measured as a straight line connecting the two most distant SOX2⁺ cells (maximal length of the epiblast). As the ED is a 3D structure, area and volume were also measured on the mask stacks corresponding to SOX2 using Imaris version 9.9.1 (Bitplane AG, Zurich, Switzerland). Presence of SOX2⁺ cells in a disc-like structure accounted for epiblast survival, T⁺ cells for the onset of gastrulation with the appearance of the PS, FOXA2⁺/SOX17⁺ cells for the establishment of the definitive endoderm (DE), and FOXA2⁺/T⁺ cells for node progenitors. Due to the axial sampling ($z=5\ \mu\text{m}$) being larger than the smallest cell diameter ($\sim 3\ \mu\text{m}$), true 3D object reconstruction was not feasible. Therefore, cell counting was performed using a 2D approach

Table 1 Details of primary and secondary antibodies, and isotype controls used for immunofluorescence.

	Antigen/marker	Host	Company	Catalogue #	Dilution	Cell lineage
Primary	SOX2	Rat	eBioscience	14-9811-82	1:100	Epiblast
	SOX17	Goat	R&D	AF1924	1:100	Hypoblast/ endoderm
	Brachyury (T)	Goat	R&D	AF2085	1:100	Mesoderm
	FOXA2/HNF3 beta	Rabbit	Cell Signaling	8186	1:100	Hypoblast/ endoderm
Isotype controls	Goat IgG	Goat	R&D	AB-108-C	Same as	-
	Rat IgG2a kappa	Rat	Invitrogen	14-4321-82	primary	-
	Rabbit IgG	Rabbit	Invitrogen	31235	antibodies	-
Secondary	Anti-goat IgG 488	Donkey	Invitrogen	A-32814	1:300	-
	Anti-rat IgG 555	Donkey	Invitrogen	A-78945	1:300	-
	Anti-rabbit IgG 647	Donkey	Invitrogen	A-31573	1:300	-

based on per-slice size filtering by area in the xy plane using the segmented mask stacks. Cells were assigned centre points (centroids) in x and y planes, for each slice in z . They were counted as the same cell if the centroids were closer than the minimum cell area and belonged to the same z slice or the adjacent one. Colocalization was qualitatively analysed by visual inspection of processed stacks by merging the two channels of interest.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed in RStudio Version 2024.12.1+563 (Posit software, Boston, MA, USA) and significance was declared at a p value ≤ 0.05 . Differences in conceptus length, ED length, and cell counts at day 16 across the different groups were analysed by one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) when data distribution was normal, followed by Tukey's post hoc comparison test. When the normality test failed (Shapiro–Wilk), statistical differences were analysed by non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by Dunn's test. Correlation between conceptus length and ED length among the groups was analysed by Pearson correlation for the groups with a normal distribution and by Spearman correlation if distribution was not normal. Categorical data between groups was analysed by Fisher's test followed by a pairwise proportion test if significant, and confidence intervals were calculated for each group using the Wilson score interval formula. SOX2⁺ cell number was analysed using linear regression models including ED volume as a covariate. To assess whether scaling relationships differed among embryo production groups, a log–log interaction model was fitted. Type III ANOVA was used to test main effects and interactions, and group-specific slopes were compared using estimated marginal trends with Benjamini–Hochberg correction. Variations in sample size among analyses were attributable to incomplete data for certain variables, resulting from technical constraints during sample processing and/or image analysis.

Results

Conceptus elongation and size classification

Conceptus length was measured in all recovered samples on day 16 in which an ED was located (80.5%, 91/113) and quartile (Q)-based size categories were established. Three groups were then defined based on length: short ($Q1 \leq 4$ cm), medium ($Q2 + Q3, 4 < 8.5$ cm), and long ($Q4 \geq 8.5$ cm) (Figure 2A and B).

The overall mean \pm SD length of conceptuses recovered intact was 6.55 ± 3.93 cm ($n=72$), but differed according to method of embryo production ($p=0.0011$). Conceptuses derived by artificial insemination (IVD) were longer than all IVP groups, including FRESH ($p=0.0014$), DT ($p=0.0293$), and VIT ($p=0.0032$) (Figure 2C). The mean \pm SD length of each group is presented in Table 2.

When categorized according to size distribution (Table 2), 53.8% of artificial insemination conceptuses were classified as long, and none were categorized as short. In contrast, IVP-derived conceptuses showed a marked shift toward shorter size categories. In the FRESH group, 40% were classified as short and 16%

as long. Similarly, DT conceptuses were predominantly short or medium (22.2% and 55.6%, respectively), with only 22.2% classified as long. VIT conceptuses showed a comparable distribution, with 25% short, 56.3% medium, and 18.8% long structures.

ED morphometry

ED length differed significantly between groups ($p=0.0001$). Artificial insemination-derived conceptuses exhibited longer EDs compared to both cryopreserved groups (DT and VIT, $p=0.029$ and $p=9.24E-05$, respectively). Additionally, ED length was greater in FRESH compared to VIT conceptuses ($p=0.012$). No differences were observed between artificial insemination and FRESH or between FRESH and DT. These data are summarized in Table 3 and Figure 3A.

In contrast to ED length, differences in disc area (Figure 3B) and volume (Figure 3C) were only detected between artificial insemination and VIT groups ($p=0.036$ and $p=0.012$, respectively); differences between artificial insemination and FRESH or artificial insemination and DT, or within IVP groups were not significant (Table 3).

Morphological assessment revealed marked differences in disc shape distribution. Although all conceptuses presented a relatively flattened disc, a high proportion of VIT conceptuses (8/15, 53.3%) presented a rounded disc morphology when observed from above, compared to artificial insemination ($p=0.028$), FRESH ($p=0.026$), and most DT discs, which exhibited the characteristic elongated/oval configuration (ED-like structure) (Table 3, Figure 3D). These findings indicate that while linear ED growth is broadly affected by embryo production method, alterations to 3D disc expansion were mostly confined to VIT conceptuses.

Correlation analysis between ED length and conceptus length revealed a significant positive association exclusively in artificial insemination conceptuses ($R=0.77$, $p=0.005$). No significant correlations were observed in FRESH ($R=0.11$, $p=0.625$), DT ($R=0.18$, $p=0.495$), or VIT ($R=0.13$, $p=0.635$) groups (Figure 2D).

Epiblast cell number and organization (SOX2)

The number of SOX2⁺ epiblast cells differed between embryos according to their method of production (Table 4, Figure 4A). Discs in artificial insemination-derived conceptuses exhibited the highest mean number of SOX2⁺ cells (3795 ± 1667 ; $n=12$), followed by FRESH (3029 ± 1511 ; $n=20$) and DT conceptuses (2897 ± 1823 ; $n=15$), while VIT conceptuses were characterized by markedly reduced numbers of SOX2⁺ cells (1637 ± 847 ; $n=16$). Both artificial insemination and FRESH conceptuses contained significantly more SOX2⁺ cells compared to VIT conceptuses ($p=0.002$ and $p=0.035$, respectively), while no differences were detected between artificial insemination, FRESH, and DT groups.

To determine whether reduced numbers of SOX2⁺ cells in VIT conceptuses reflected intrinsic alterations in epiblast allocation or were secondary to differences in disc size, SOX2⁺ cell number was analysed using disc volume as a covariate (Figure 4B). Disc

Figure 2 Conceptus elongation dynamics at day 16 in cattle following artificial insemination (AI) or the transfer of a FRESH or cryopreserved [slow frozen for direct transfer (DT) or vitrified (VIT)]. (A) Quartile distribution of day 16 (D16) conceptus length across all recovered samples. (B) Representative brightfield images (1 \times) of intact D16 conceptuses immediately after uterine flushing for short (S), medium (M), and long (L) categories based on quartiles. (C) Graphical representation of the length distribution of the conceptuses across IVD (AI) and IVP (FRESH, DT and VIT) groups. Bars represent mean \pm SD. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$. (D) Scatter plot showing embryonic disc (ED) length against conceptus length. The dashed-black line corresponds to a linear regression model fitted to the data. Pearson's (FRESH) and Spearman's correlation test (AI, DT and VIT), $p < 0.05$.

volume was a highly significant predictor of SOX2⁺ cell number ($p = 0.035$), whereas neither the effect of group nor the interaction between group and volume reached statistical significance ($p = 0.61$ and $p = 0.59$, respectively). These findings indicate that epiblast cell number scales proportionally with disc volume across all groups.

When conceptuses were classified according to size category (short, medium, long), significant differences in SOX2⁺ cell number were observed ($p = 0.0038$) (Figure 4C). Long conceptuses exhibited a higher number of SOX2⁺ cells compared to short conceptuses ($p = 0.0029$), whereas medium conceptuses showed intermediate values.

Table 2 Conceptus length (mean \pm SD) and size distribution of day 16 bovine conceptuses.

Group	<i>n</i>	Conceptus length (cm)	Short (Q1 \leq 4 cm)	Medium (Q2 + Q3 < 8.5 cm)	Long (Q4 \geq 8.5 cm)
AI	13	10.5 \pm 4.45 ^a	0 (0%)	6 (46.2%)	7 (53.8%)
FRESH	25	5.40 \pm 3.18 ^b	10 (40%)	11 (44%)	4 (16%)
DT	18	6.22 \pm 3.34 ^b	4 (22.2%)	10 (55.6%)	4 (22.2%)
VIT	16	5.55 \pm 3.43 ^b	4 (25%)	9 (56.3%)	3 (18.8%)
Total	72	6.55 \pm 3.93	18 (25%)	36 (50%)	18 (25%)

Note: AI = artificial Insemination; DT = direct transfer; Q = quartile; VIT = vitrification.

^{a, b, c} Values with different letters in the same column differ significantly. Kruskal–Wallis test for conceptus length; $p < 0.05$.

Table 3 Embryonic disc (ED) morphogenetic features at day 16 in bovine conceptuses.

Group	<i>n</i>	ED length (μ m)	<i>n</i>	Area (mm ²)	Volume (mm ³)	Normal ED-like structure
AI	12	534.71 \pm 183.11 ^a	12	0.66 \pm 0.36 ^a	0.0015 \pm 0.0008 ^a	12 (100%) ^a
FRESH	28	399.09 \pm 83.10 ^{a, b}	20	0.55 \pm 0.24	0.0012 \pm 0.0006	19 (95%)
DT	17	352.72 \pm 113.02 ^{b, c}	17	0.52 \pm 0.45	0.0011 \pm 0.0008	15 (88.2%)
VIT	18	298.65 \pm 99.91 ^c	15	0.38 \pm 0.36 ^b	0.0007 \pm 0.0004 ^b	7 (47.1%) ^b
TOTAL	75	386.17 \pm 135.35	64	0.53 \pm 0.36	0.0011 \pm 0.0007	53 (82.8%)

Note: AI = artificial insemination; DT = direct transfer; VIT = vitrification.

^{a, b, c} Values with different letters in the same column differ significantly. Normal ED-like structure was defined as an elongated/oval flattened disc shape. Kruskal–Wallis test for ED length and area; ANOVA for ED volume; $p < 0.05$.

Onset and pattern of gastrulation (T)

To evaluate the onset of gastrulation, we assessed the presence of a posterior T⁺ cell cluster within the ED. EDs were classified as either positive or negative for a clearly defined posterior T⁺ domain. The proportion of conceptuses exhibiting a T⁺ cluster was high across all groups, with 100% of artificial insemination conceptuses showing a posterior cluster, compared to 84.6% in FRESH, 88.9% in DT, and 87.5% in VIT conceptuses (Table 4). Fisher's exact test revealed no differences in the proportion of T⁺ conceptuses among groups, indicating that the initiation of gastrulation, as defined by posterior T expression, was not significantly affected by embryo production method.

Although gastrulation onset occurred in most embryos regardless of production method, qualitative differences in spatial organization were observed. In artificial insemination and FRESH conceptuses, T⁺ cells formed a compact cluster localized to the posterior pole of the ED (Figure 5A). In contrast, DT and VIT conceptuses more frequently exhibited a less defined pattern, with T⁺ cells appearing more dispersed and less tightly restricted to the posterior region.

Hypoblast differentiation toward endodermal lineages (SOX17/FOXA2)

To assess hypoblast differentiation, we examined the expression of the endoderm-associated marker SOX17 in day 16 EDs. SOX17⁺ cells were detected throughout the hypoblast layer underlying the SOX2⁺ epiblast in most discs from all embryo production groups. In addition to this broad hypoblast expression, a subset of

cells, intensely labelled for SOX17⁺, frequently formed a localized cluster toward the posterior region of the disc, spatially associated with the T⁺ domain (Figure 5B).

The proportion of EDs displaying a posterior SOX17⁺ domain was similar across groups (71.4% of artificial insemination, 72.7% of FRESH, 83.3% of DT, and 55.6% of VIT conceptuses). Statistical comparison of proportions did not reveal any differences among groups (Fisher's exact test, $p = 0.778$). The data are summarised in Table 4.

FOXA2 distribution relative to SOX17 was evaluated qualitatively from merged stacks and three distinct disc patterns were identified: (i) domain-like/anterior, (ii) central, and (iii) dispersed. EDs displaying a domain-like/anterior pattern exhibited a FOXA2⁺ enriched domain adjacent to SOX17⁺ clusters and colocalization toward the centre of the disc with stronger enrichment toward the anterior pole (Figure 6A and B). In contrast, in the second group FOXA2/SOX17 colocalization was mainly restricted to the central region, without clear anterior enrichment or a defined clustered domain. In EDs with a dispersed pattern, only a few scattered cells were colocalized, without a recognizable spatial organization. The majority of artificial insemination (3/4, 75%) and FRESH (3/5, 60%) EDs presented the domain-like/anterior pattern, whereas 50% of VIT embryos displayed dispersed FOXA2/SOX17 colocalization (2/4). Central patterns were observed at lower frequencies across groups (artificial insemination: 1/4, 25%; FRESH: 1/5, 20%; VIT: 1/4, 25%). Two VIT conceptuses, were not included in the classification: one conceptus lacked detectable FOXA2 expression and one displayed FOXA2/SOX17 overlap only outside the ED. The data are summarised in Table 5 and Figure 6C.

Finally, FOXA2 spatial organization was qualitatively assessed relative to T expression. In all artificial insemination ($n = 4$) and FRESH

Figure 3 Embryonic disc (ED) development in bovine conceptuses. Distribution of (A) ED length, (B) area, and (C) volume among artificial insemination (AI)- and in vitro-produced groups [FRESH, slow frozen for direct transfer (DT), or vitrified (VIT)]. Bars represent mean \pm SD. (D) Representative maximal projections stained for SOX2 (epiblast) showing shape configuration on day 16 conceptuses from a dorsal and a lateral view. Scale bar at 20 μm . * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$.

Table 4 Epiblast number of cells stained for SOX2 (mean \pm SD) and proportion discs exhibiting T⁺ and SOX17⁺ clusters spatially localized toward the posterior region in day 16 bovine conceptuses.

Group	<i>n</i>	SOX2 ⁺ cells	T ⁺ cluster (PS)	SOX17 ⁺ cluster
AI	12	3795 \pm 1667 ^a	6/6 (100%)	5/7 (71.4%)
FRESH	20	3029 \pm 1511 ^a	11/13 (84.6%)	8/11 (72.7%)
DT	15	2897 \pm 1823	8/9 (88.9%)	5/6 (83.3%)
VIT	16	1637 \pm 847 ^b	7/8 (87.5%)	5/9 (55.6%)
TOTAL	63	2790 \pm 1636	32/36 (88.9%)	23/33 (69.7%)

Note: AI = artificial insemination; DT = direct transfer; PS = primitive streak; VIT = vitrification.

^{a, b}Values with different letters in the same column differ significantly. ANOVA $p < 0.05$. Fisher's test $p > 0.05$.

($n=7$) discs evaluated, FOXA2⁺ cells colocalizing with T⁺ cells were detected immediately anterior to the T⁺ cluster region, forming a consistent pattern anterior to the PS (Figure 6D). In contrast, VIT ($n=3$) discs lacked this spatial organization: one ED showed only a few dispersed cells colocalizing, one showed no apparent colocalization, and one lacked detectable FOXA2 expression.

Discussion

The present study provides a comprehensive characterization of early ED development and cell lineage specification in bovine embryos during gastrulation, and compares lineage patterning between IVD (artificial insemination) or IVP conceptuses. Results indicate that while key developmental processes, including

Figure 4 Quantification of epiblast cells in elongating conceptuses. (A) Graphical representation of epiblast (SOX2⁺) cell numbers by group [artificial insemination (AI), FRESH, slow frozen for direct transfer (DT) or vitrified (VIT) and (B) by quartile-based conceptus size category (short, S; medium, M; long, L). (C) Log–log scatter plot with regression lines showing the relationship between embryonic disc volume and SOX2⁺ epiblast cell number. Bars represent mean ± SD. ANOVA and Kruskal–Wallis test; **p* < 0.05, ***p* < 0.01.

epiblast expansion, gastrulation initiation, and hypoblast differentiation, occur in both artificial insemination- and IVP-derived conceptuses, the latter exhibit altered elongation dynamics and spatial organization of developmental domains.

In vitro production offers several advantages over traditional multiple ovulation embryo transfer, including greater flexibility in sire selection enabling the generation of multiple pregnancies from elite dam-sire combinations, increased embryo yield per unit time per genetically elite female, and the ability to use oocytes from prepubertal females, thereby reducing the generation interval as well as allowing more efficient use of rare or high-cost semen straws (e.g., sex-sorted semen) (Crowe et al., 2021). Despite these benefits, significant challenges relating to pregnancy loss after ET, particularly after cryopreservation of IVP embryos, and concerns regarding peri- and post-natal health and developmental outcomes of IVP offspring, continue to limit the wider adoption of this technology. The present findings provide morphological and cellular evidence that may help explain

these limitations, showing that IVP-derived conceptuses exhibit impaired elongation and altered ED development at a critical stage of early pregnancy.

Building on earlier reports of impaired post-hatching development and altered transcriptomic profiles in bovine IVP (Bertolini et al., 2002, Machado et al., 2013, Behrens et al., 2025) and somatic cell nuclear transfer-derived embryos (Rodríguez-Alvarez et al., 2010), in the current study the average length of IVP-derived day 16 conceptuses was shorter than that of artificial insemination-derived counterparts. Moreover, our data indicate that reduced elongation is accompanied by disrupted coordination between TE and ED growth. Specifically, in contrast to artificial insemination-derived pregnancies, where the growth of embryonic and extra-embryonic compartments was strongly correlated, ED length and overall conceptus length were not correlated in the IVP groups, suggesting a loss of coordinated growth. Our findings support an earlier report describing shorter extra-embryonic membranes in IVP-derived days

Figure 5 Expression patterns of T and SOX17 in elongating bovine embryonic discs around gastrulation. Representative maximal projections of embryonic discs from day 16 conceptuses derived by artificial insemination (AI)- and in vitro-produced groups [FRESH, slow frozen for direct transfer (DT), and vitrified (VIT)]. Immunofluorescence analysis was performed for SOX2 (epiblast) in combination with (A) T-box-containing transcription factor brachyury (T) (primitive streak) or (B) SOX17 (hypoblast/endodermal lineages). Scale bar=20 μm. A↔P denotes anterior to posterior orientation.

26–35 pregnancies compared to IVD counterparts (Pedersen et al., 2020), and suggest that these deficits arise much earlier, at the initiation of elongation. Conceptus length has been shown to directly influence endometrial signalling and pregnancy

establishment, as short conceptuses induce a suboptimal transcription response in the endometrium compared to long conceptuses (Sánchez et al. 2019). This is likely due to factors secreted by the embryos themselves, as in an age-matched study, short

Table 5 Spatial distribution proportions of FOXA2 relative to SOX17 and co-localization patterns in day 16 bovine embryonic discs.

Group	<i>n</i>	Domain-like/ anterior	Central	Dispersed
AI	4	3 (75%)	1 (25%)	0 (0%)
FRESH	5	3 (60%)	1 (20%)	1 (20%)
VIT	4	1 (25%)	1 (25%)	2 (50%)
TOTAL	13	7 (53.8%)	3 (23.1%)	3 (23.1%)

Note. AI = artificial insemination; DT = direct transfer; VIT = vitrification.

and long bovine conceptuses were found to exhibit distinct transcriptomic profiles (Barnwell et al., 2016). Previously, we showed that interferon tau secretion *in vitro* is highly correlated with conceptus size (Rizos et al., 2012); long conceptuses upregulate many interferon-stimulated genes in the endometrium that short conceptuses fail to induce (Sánchez et al., 2019). These transcriptomic differences may reflect subsequent development fate, suggesting a link between conceptus length, interferon tau signalling, and pregnancy success. Embryo source is also highly relevant, as earlier studies have described its impact on several canonical pathways and genes involved in uterine receptivity and conceptus placentation, altering embryo–maternal communication in cloned and, to a lesser extent, IVF-derived pregnancies compared to artificial insemination counterparts (Mansouri-Attia et al., 2009; Bauersachs et al., 2009).

Extending this further, in a day 16 conceptus–endometrium co-culture model, Peterson et al. (2025) reported that IVP conceptuses exhibit transcriptomic enrichment for genes linked to abnormal embryonic/fetal development and elicit distinct, partly inflammatory endometrial responses, indicating that elongating IVP conceptuses remain biochemically and functionally different from IVD conceptuses, presumably contributing to pregnancy loss. In this context, the reduced elongation observed in IVP-derived conceptuses in the present study may contribute to impaired embryo–maternal signalling and reduced pregnancy success.

Beyond differences in elongation, epiblast cell numbers were lower in vitrified conceptuses. Moreover, this was primarily attributable to reduced ED size rather than defects in lineage allocation *per se*, suggesting that developmental impairment in IVP embryos is driven by overall growth restriction rather than failure of cell fate specification. This distinction is critical, as it suggests epiblast lineage commitment remains largely intact following IVP, while processes regulating growth and expansion are compromised.

Nonetheless, IVP also impacts the spatial organization of developmental lineages. Although the initiation of gastrulation was largely conserved across groups, a key finding of the present study is the altered spatial organization of lineage-specific markers in IVP-derived conceptuses. In conceptuses derived from artificial insemination or fresh IVP embryos, T, SOX17, and FOXA2 labelling was organized as anterior–posterior patterning. However, this organization was frequently disrupted following cryopreservation, particularly vitrification. The presence of a posterior T⁺ domain in all groups indicates that the initiation of gastrulation is largely preserved, regardless of embryo origin. This is consistent with previous descriptions of anterior–posterior patterning during gastrulation in sheep and cattle; as the ED elongates and gastrulation begins, T is expressed in cells at the posterior epiblast, which start to ingress through the PS and form nascent mesoderm (Pérez-Gómez et al.,

2021). At the same time, Eomesodermin (EOMES) colocalizes with T in the posterior region of the ED, while SOX2 expression becomes progressively restricted to the anterior epiblast, opposite the T/EOMES domain. These observations are consistent with the proposed staging system for post-hatching IVP bovine embryos from days 11 to 15 post-IVF (van Leeuwen et al., 2015), demonstrating a conserved onset of posterior Nodal Growth Differentiation Factor (NODAL), EOMES, and T expression and PS formation. However, comparisons with mouse (Ding et al., 1998, Brennan et al., 2001, Rivera-Pérez & Magnuson, 2005) revealed that although gene expression programmes at the onset of gastrulation are largely conserved, species-specific features of embryonic asymmetry, driven by extra-embryonic tissues such as the hypoblast and trophoblast, have diverged both genetically and morphologically.

Regardless of embryo source, the majority of discs exhibited a posterior expression pattern for SOX17. However, this pattern was less organized and occurred less frequently in conceptuses derived from vitrified embryos. SOX17 and FOXA2 have been defined as lineage differentiation markers for migrated hypoblast and DE in elongating bovine and ovine conceptuses (Pérez-Gómez et al., 2021). The two markers were predominantly colocalized in the anterior pole of EDs in artificial insemination-derived and fresh IVP conceptuses, but this spatial organization was not observed in vitrified-derived discs. In fact the cells exhibiting colocalization of SOX17 and FOXA2 were frequently dispersed. In line with this, *in vitro* post-hatching development systems supported bovine hypoblast migration and epiblast survival but frequently showed apoptosis/necrosis, indicating that endoderm lineages can form, yet patterning and survival are sensitive to culture conditions (Ramos-Ibeas et al., 2020), which may compromise correct axis formation. Similarly, an earlier investigation of lineage commitment in porcine peri-gastrulating embryos elucidated the spatial localization of T and FOXA2 (Wolf et al., 2011). The authors reported strong hypoblast/DE FOXA2 expression at all developmental stages examined and co-expression of T and FOXA2 in the anterior PS. Expression of T and FOXA2 was consistently colocalized anterior to the PS in artificial insemination-derived and fresh EDs. However, this spatial organization was absent in vitrified EDs. Making an analogy to mouse data, where T and FOXA2 co-expression characterized node/notochord progenitors (Burtscher & Lickert, 2009, Harrelson et al., 2012), Wolf et al. interpreted this spatial colocalization of T and FOXA2 expression as a presumptive node/organiser domain, thus its absence in the discs of conceptuses derived from vitrified IVP embryos indicates their lack of the necessary molecular signalling for node and notochord progenitor formation.

Our description of altered elongation and lineage organization is consistent with molecular evidence from previous studies that have demonstrated that, in cattle, IVP and cryopreservation introduce persistent alterations in embryo cell lineages and overall developmental quality. An integrated transcriptome–methylome meta-analysis of several datasets identified TE genes important for conceptus elongation and focal adhesion that are deregulated in early conceptuses derived from IVP versus multiple ovulation embryo transfer embryos, mechanistically linking IVP status with impaired elongation and reduced post-transfer survival (Rabaglino et al., 2021). While, multi-omic analyses of day 15 bovine conceptuses reveal that IVP embryos, compared with their IVD counterparts, exhibit aberrant methylation and down-regulated expression of genes governing somitogenesis,

Figure 6 Expression pattern and spatial distribution of FOXA2 relative to SOX17 (domain-like/anterior pattern) and T-box-containing transcription factor brachyury (T). Representative maximal projection from (A) a dorsal and (B) a lateral view of an embryonic disc stained for SOX17 and FOXA2 (hypoblast/endodermal lineages). Dashed-squares in white mark the regions positive for SOX17 or FOXA2 only. Arrowheads point to FOXA2⁺/SOX17⁻ cells (red), FOXA2⁺/SOX17⁺ cells (green), and FOXA2⁻/SOX17⁺ cells (yellow). (C) Graphical representation of the percentage of discs showing the different identified distribution patterns of FOXA2/SOX17 co-localization from artificial insemination (AI), FRESH, and vitrified (VIT) day 16 discs. (D) Representative maximal projection from an embryonic disc stained for T and FOXA2 (hypoblast/endodermal lineages). Arrowheads point to FOXA2⁺/T⁻ cells (red), FOXA2⁺/T⁺ cells (green), and FOXA2⁻/SOX17⁺ cells (yellow). Scale bar, 20 μ m. A ↔ P denotes anterior to posterior orientation.

mesoderm formation, gastrulation, and key Bone Morphogenetic Protein (BMP)/Wnt pathways in both ED and extra-embryonic tissues, consistent with impaired lineage specification and reduced

developmental competence and pregnancy rates (Behrens et al., 2025), our data indicate that these defects are exacerbated by vitrification. Recently, Angel-Velez et al. (2023) showed that vitrified

bovine oocytes are associated with severely compromised blastocyst development, with abnormal morphokinetics and increased developmental arrest, supporting a stronger impact of vitrification on lineage integrity and embryo quality. Importantly, such alterations persist beyond the pre-implantation stage.

In summary, at day 16, both artificial insemination and IVP conceptuses exhibited key developmental processes, including epiblast expansion, hypoblast differentiation, and initiation of gastrulation marked by T expression. However, IVP conceptuses showed reduced elongation capacity, and those derived from vitrified embryos in particular displayed smaller and morphologically altered EDs. Although epiblast cell number scaled proportionally with disc size across groups, suggesting preserved lineage allocation, IVP embryos exhibited disrupted coordination between ED and TE growth, as well as altered spatial organization of key developmental markers (T, SOX17, FOXA2). Overall, these findings indicate that while fundamental developmental events are maintained, in vitro embryo production may impair elongation and growth dynamics, and spatial patterning during critical stages of early pregnancy, potentially contributing to embryonic loss.

Author contributions

Sara Núñez-Torvisco (Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing—original draft, Writing—review & editing, Visualization), Ana Clara Canto Souza (Investigation), Michael McDonald (Investigation), Laura Thompson (Investigation), Reintje van Wezel (Investigation), Trudee Fair (Conceptualization, Writing—review & editing), and Pat Lonergan (Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing—review & editing, Funding acquisition)

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

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Data availability

All data underlying this article are available in the article.

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